

A study on the adsorption behaviour of carbofuran on tin(IV) arsenophosphate H^+ , Na^+ and Ca^{2+} forms

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The adsorption behaviour of carbofuran has been studied on tin(IV) arsenophosphate cation exchanger in H^+ , Na^+ and Ca^{2+} forms at 25 and 50°. The adsorption isotherms of carbofuran follow the Freundlich adsorption model and yield 'L' class isotherms. The order of adsorption of carbofuran is maximum in H^+ form of the cation exchanger. The thermodynamic parameters have also been calculated for predicting the nature of adsorption.

Adsorption is one of the major processes which affects the behaviour of pesticides on soils¹⁻³. The adsorption of pesticides on soils is also influenced by the presence of ions. Adsorption of pesticides on inorganic ion exchangers is also of interest as some of these materials have greater adsorption potential for carbofuran (2,3-dihydro-2,2-dimethyl-7-benzofuranyl methyl carbonate) as compared to soils⁴. The present study was designed to investigate adsorption behaviour of carbofuran on H^+ , Na^+ and Ca^{2+} tin(IV) arsenophosphate using the theoretical approach of Biggar and Cheung and others.

Results and Discussion

The adsorption of carbofuran by tin(IV) arsenophosphates at 25° is presented in Fig. 1. The adsorption

Fig. 1. Plots of adsorbed carbofuran versus time on tin(IV) arsenophosphate at 25°

Fig. 2. Adsorption isotherms of carbofuran on tin(IV) arsenophosphate (H^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{2+}) cation exchanger

isotherms of carbofuran by three ionic forms of tin(IV) arsenophosphate ion exchanger are presented in Fig. 2. The isotherms for all the three forms of ion exchanger are L-type at 25 and 50°, which suggests that initially more sites in the exchanger are available to be filled with carbofuran and with the process, it becomes gradually difficult to find vacant sites. In all cases the adsorption is higher at lower temperature, probably due to weaker attractive force at higher temperature.

The adsorption behaviour of carbofuran on the exchanger can be expressed by the Freundlich equation,

$$x/m = KC^{1/n} \quad (1)$$

where, x/m is the surface concentration of carbofuran in m -

moles per g of the exchanger, C the equilibrium concentration of carbofuran in mmol per ml, K and $1/n$ are constants evaluated from the intercept and slope of the straight line plots of $\log C_e$ vs $\log C_s$ (Fig. 3) respectively, fitted to the points by the least-square method. The values are summarized in Table 1. The values of K are generally greater at 25° than at 50°. The results are in accordance with the earlier work^{3,5}.

Thermodynamic equilibrium constant K_0 (or the thermodynamic distribution coefficient) for the adsorption reaction can be defined as

$$K_0 = \frac{a_s}{a_e} = \frac{\gamma_s C_s}{\gamma_e C_e}$$

where, a_s is the activity of the adsorbed solute, a_e the activity of the solute in the equilibrium solution, C_s the carbofuran adsorbed mmol per ml of solvent in contact with the adsorbent surface, C_e the carbofuran mmol per ml of solvent in equilibrium solution, γ_s and γ_e are the activity coefficients of the solute on the surface and in the equilibrium solution respectively.

Fig. 3. Freundlich isotherms of carbofuran adsorption on tin(IV) arsenophosphate (H^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{2+}) cation exchanger.

Fig. 4. Plots of $\ln C_s/C_e$ vs C_s on tin(IV) arsenophosphate (H^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{2+}) cation exchanger.

For very dilute solution equation (2) may be written as

$$\frac{C_s}{C_e} = \frac{a_s}{a_e} = K_0 \quad (3)$$

Values of K_0 are obtained by plotting $\ln (C_s/C_e)$ vs C_s and extrapolating to zero C_s by graphic method². The error in K_0 was estimated from $SD = (C_s/C_e) \ln 10$, SD of $\ln C_s/C_e$ ⁶. First of all a straight line is fitted through the points by the least-square method and its intersection with the vertical axis gives the value of K_0 (Fig. 4). The ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° values were calculated using usual expressions (Table 2). The negative value of standard enthalpy change indicates that carbofuran-exchange interaction is exothermic. Since the free energy changes are negative and are accompanied by a positive entropy change, the reactions are spontaneous with high affinity for carbofuran⁷ in all forms of the exchanger at both the temperatures. This is supported by the isotherms shown in Fig. 2.

Table 1. Freundlich isotherm constants K and $1/n$ for the adsorption of carbofuran on different forms of tin(IV) arsenophosphate cation exchangers

Form	At 25°		At 50°	
	K	$1/n$	K	$1/n$
H^+	0.15	0.52	0.08	0.51
Na^+	16.37	0.86	0.05	0.47
Ca^{2+}	1.19	0.66	0.02	0.39

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of different forms of carbofuran on tin(IV) arsenophosphate cation exchangers

Forms	K_0		ΔG° kJ mol ⁻¹		ΔH° kJ	ΔS° JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	25°	50°	25°	50°		
H^+	479.4	227.9	-15.3	-14.6	-23.8	28.6
Na^+	135.6	262.1	-12.2	-15.0	-21.1	111.8
Ca^{2+}	173.4	325.1	-12.8	-15.6	-20.1	110.6

Experimental

Tin chloride (I.P.H. Polskee Odezynnik Chemiezne) and Carbofuran/Furadon-3G (Rallis India) were used. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

A water-bath incubator shaker having a temperature control of $\pm 0.1^\circ$ was used for all the equilibrium studies. A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer was used.

Tin(IV) arsenophosphate was prepared by mixing equal volumes of 0.1 M solutions of tin(IV) chloride, sodium arsenate and sodium phosphate. The pH of the mixture was adjusted to 0.0 with nitric acid. The gel thus prepared was kept at room temperature for 24 h, filtered, washed with demineralised water and dried at 40°. The dried material was crushed and converted into hydrogen form by keeping it in 1 M HNO_3 . The material was finally washed with demineralised water and dried at 40°. The ion exchange capacity of the thus processed material was found to be 1.75 meq/g as reported earlier⁸. The material was also con-

verted into Na^+ and Ca^{2+} forms by passing 1.0 M NaNO_3 and 1.0 M $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solutions through columns of tin(IV) arsenophosphate.

Adsorption studies : The fractions (0.2 g) of all three forms of the exchanger (H^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{2+}) were kept at desired temperatures (25 and 50°) followed by addition of carbofuran solution (2000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) in varying amounts (0–10 ml). The total volume was brought to 20 ml by adding demineralised water and the equilibrium was attained in 2 h. The supernatant was then analysed spectrophotometrically³.

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